
Review

Clinical Outcome and Safety of Cox-Maze IV Procedure for Atrial Fibrillation Associated with Congenital Heart Disease: A Case Report and Literature Review

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Abstract: Introduction: Atrial Fibrillation in adult patients presenting with congenital heart disease (ACHD) is the prime cause of morbidity and mortality. In this sub group of people, the majority of hospital admissions are caused by atrial fibrillation and according to some studies, it represents about 20-25% of late mortalities¹. Because the need for further cardiac operations is frequent in ACHD, the Cox-maze IV procedure (CM4) performed together with other cardiac procedures has shown to be successful in the restoration of normal sinus rhythm (NSR). The aim of this case report is to evaluate the Maze operation's safety and early clinical outcomes in the treatment of symptomatic and medically recurrent AF and also assess the advantage and risks of concomitant congenital heart surgery (Atrial Septal defect ASD) with the Cox-Maze procedure.

Case presentation: Presenting a 58 year old male with congenital atrial septal defect with associated atrial fibrillation who successfully underwent a COX MAZE 4 procedure with complete cessation of atrial fibrillation. The patient had no complications after surgery and was discharged 22 days post-operative. He underwent ASD closure and left atrial appendage (LAA) closure 3 years prior indicated for atrial fibrillation and stroke.

Discussion: AF is frequently seen in patients with ASD, the high incidence of AF in patients with ASD is linked to chronic volume overload as a result of a left-to-right atrial shunt, resulting in geometrical and electrical remodeling of both upper chambers of the heart (atria) and the incidence of ASD-associated AF is also firmly related with age². Although a standalone closure of ASD may lead to restoring of normal sinus rhythm, it is widely agreed upon that surgical intervention for AF should be performed on ASD closure, this is particularly so in elderly patients with chronic AF and enlarged right atrium².

The ablation-assisted Cox-maze IV procedure (CM4), established several years back, has dramatically reduced and made easy the operation and has led to a reduction in morbidity and mortality attributed with the Cox Maze Procedure. The CM4 currently is the gold standard surgical treatment for AF, with a 93% freedom from AF and 85% freedom from AF and antiarrhythmic drugs (AAD) at 1 year, and a 78% freedom from AF and 66% freedom from AF and AAD at 5 years³.

Conclusion: Cox Maze 4 operation for the treatment of Afib in ACHD is a safe and an effective procedure. The Cox Maze 4 has an excellent efficacy at maintaining normal sinus rhythm.

Keywords: ACHD; Adult Congenital Heart Disease, CM4; Cox Maze IV, ASD; Atrial Septal Defect, AF; Atrial Fibrillation, AAD; Anti arrhythmia Drug, LAA; Left atrial appendage

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Accepted: 17 May, 2023; **Published:** 25 May, 2023

How to cite this article: Mbenkum Achiri Tardzenyuy, Cai Cheng, Wajeehullahi Akilu, Xiantao Ma, Yi Feng, Shiliang li (2023). *Clinical Outcome and Safety of Cox-Maze IV Procedure for Atrial Fibrillation Associated with Congenital Heart Disease: A Case Report and Literature Review*. *North American Academic Research*, 6(5), 61-66. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7967550>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

Atrial fibrillation (AF) is accepted to be the most sustained cardiac arrhythmia globally, with a rise in incidence associated with the patient's age. This is most popular heart arrhythmia associated with an adverse prognosis. It occurs in men with a greater prevalence as opposed to women³. Atrial fibrillation being one of the most common comorbidities in middle-aged and older patients having an atrial septal defect (ASD)². There is a growing population of adults who are having congenital heart disease (ACHD). Early diagnosis, advancement in surgical technique, and medical therapy have shown to bring about increase in the overall survival to the adulthood of newborns affected by moderate to complex congenital heart diseases. According to some studies, it is estimated that in Europe, there is an ACHD population of 2.3 million, which shows to be significantly more in number than the pediatric congenital heart disease (CHD) population⁴.

Atrial fibrillation develops at a younger age in those with ASD as opposed to normal population, and according to some studies, its prevalence is as high as 50% after 60 years old. Patients with ASD and atrial fibrillation AF don't only remain at high risk of stroke and bleeding complications due to anticoagulants, but they also can develop heart failure, particularly older patients. Furthermore, a recent study demonstrated that atrial fibrillation was an independent determinant of mortality, and heart failure was a major cause of death in adult patients having ASD.²

The natural course of an unrepaired atrial septal defect (ASD) is complicated frequently by the development of atrial fibrillation (AF), and the incidence of ASD associated AF strongly correlates with age. Because uncontrolled AF brings about an increased risk of thromboembolism and cerebral stroke, it is of the paramount importance to bring about a restoration in normal sinus rhythm (NSR) on ASD closure for an improved and better long-term outcome.⁵

Current management is similar to that in patients without ACHD and this includes medical therapy, device therapy, catheter ablation, and surgery interventions such as the Maze procedure.⁴

The prolonged use of antiarrhythmic drugs (AADs) possess a limited role in this special subgroup of patients due to insufficient of safety data and the risk of potentially detrimental proarrhythmic effects. Catheter ablation of Atrial Fibrillation is also associated with increased acute success rate but significant long-term recurrences, this is more so in adult patients with CHD. The Cox Maze IV surgical procedure is a potential option in patients who suffer from severe symptomatic AFib recurrences, despite numerous percutaneous attempts or for patients who are already candidate to heart surgery⁴.

The Cox-maze procedure has been demonstrated to be an efficacious surgical treatment of AF. Originally introduced by Dr. James Cox in 1987 as a “cut-and-sew” operation, it underwent several revisions on the basis of extensive clinical experience and investigations in animals. The ablation-assisted Cox-maze IV procedure (CM4), introduced several years back, has dramatically reduced and made easy the operation and has brought about a reduction in morbidity and mortality attributed with it. The CM4 is currently the gold standard surgical treatment for AF, with a 93% freedom from AF and 85% freedom from AF and antiarrhythmic drugs (AAD) at 1 year, and a 78% freedom from AF and 66% freedom from AF and AAD at 5 years. According to several studies, CM4 has been demonstrated not to add significantly to the morbidity or mortality when used in conjunction with other cardiac surgeries³.

Presentation

Presenting a 58 year old male patient who presented at the outpatient department of Tongji Hospital of Tongji Medical College complaining of fatigue, shortness of breath, and dizziness. Patient complaint of having the above mentioned symptoms for about 3 years and these symptoms were aggravated by exercise. He was on no special treatment at the time consultation.

In patient's home town hospital inpatient clinic, a Doppler ultrasound of the heart was done which showed patent foramen ovale and mitral insufficiency and he had undergone a left atrial appendage closure and closure of the foramen ovale which were performed 3 years ago for atrial fibrillation and stroke. Patient denies having hypertension, diabetes mellitus and hepatitis. Patient is a known smoker smoking 1 pack daily for the past 20 years and a moderate drinker. Physical examinations were unremarkable and patient was admitted and planned for surgery with admission diagnosis based on the doppler ultrasound of valvular heart disease, and also ecg findings of atrial fibrillation with patients past ultrasound of patent foramen ovale.

Hospitalization day 1, patient was stable. A control ECG was done confirming atrial fibrillation and a color Doppler echocardiography was done showing

- 1) No residual shunt found after atrial septal occlusion
- 2) Bilateral atrial enlargement, with moderate to severe tricuspid regurgitation and mild to moderate mitral regurgitation.

Hospitalization day 4, patient underwent a Cox Maze 4 Procedure.

Surgical procedure

Patient given general anesthesia and placed in the supine position on the surgical bed, routine disinfection and surgical prepping of was done. The sternum was split open lengthwise through a median incision and the mediastinum was exposed. The pericardium was cut and suspended for better exposure of the heart. The superior and inferior vena cavae were catheterized respectively with routine cardiopulmonary bypass established. The right atrium opened and the radiofrequency ablation (bipolar) performed along the established routes. Left atrial appendage occluder and left atrial septal occluder were found after the left atrial incision and there was no obvious shunt or breakage found. Radio frequency ablation (bipolar) along the established route on the left atrial surface was done. Exploration of the mitral valve done with no abnormality of the valve structure. Mild regurgitation was seen with a decision not to do mitral valvuloplasty made. Exploration of the tricuspid valve was done showing a large reflux and a tricuspid valvuloplasty was done. Right atrial and left atria incisions were sutured with 4-0 prolene sutures. Patient was weaned from the cardiopulmonary bypass in standard fashion and the mediastinal drains placed. The sternum was fixed in place with 6 steel wires and the skin closed and dressed. Patient was taken to the ICU and monitored regularly with routine ECG showing normal sinus rhythm. When he was stable, he was moved to the wards and was constantly monitored and eventually discharged home in normal sinus rhythm with adequate medication, He presented at 3 months and 6 months follow up with normal sinus rhythm.

Fig 1; Aortic Cannulation, Bicaval Cannulation.

Fig 2; Right anterior atria wall ablation.

Fig 3; ASD occluder seen in the left atrial chamber.

Fig 4; Exploration of mitral Valve and ASD Occluder.

Discussion

Atrial fibrillation (AF) is considered the most common sustained arrhythmia globally, with an increasing incidence corresponding to patient age. It is the most common cardiac arrhythmia and is associated with an adverse prognosis.³

AF develops at a younger age in those with ASD than in the normal population, and according to some studies, its prevalence is as high as 50% after 60 years old. Patients with ASD and AF not only remain at risk of stroke and bleeding complications due to anticoagulants, but they also can develop heart failure, especially older patients. Furthermore, a recent study showed that Atrial Fibrillation was an independent determinant of mortality, and heart failure was a major cause of death in adult patients with ASD.²

The high incidence of AF in patients with ASD is related to chronic volume overload due to a left-to-right atrial shunt, resulting in geometrical and electrical remodeling of both atria.²

Current therapy is similar to patients without ACHD and this includes medical therapy, device therapy, catheter ablation, and surgery interventions.⁴

Due to the poor efficacy of most common sustained antiarrhythmic drugs and their adverse side effects in the management of AF, there has been considerable interest in the interventional treatment of AF, including both catheter ablation and surgical ablation (SA). According to several studies, the most effective surgical option for the management of AF has been the Cox-Maze procedure (CMP), introduced by James Cox and colleagues in 1987. The “cut-and-sew” version, known as the CMP-III, involves making surgical incisions in both the left and right atria to interrupt the macro-reentrant circuits thought to be responsible for AF propagation⁶.

The ablation-assisted Cox-maze IV procedure (CM4), introduced several years ago, has dramatically reduced and simplified the operation and has decreased morbidity and mortality attributed with it. The CM4 is currently the gold standard surgical treatment for AF, with a 93% freedom from AF and 85% freedom from AF and anti arrhythmic drugs(AAD) at 1 year, and a 78% freedom from AF and 66% freedom from AF and AAD at 5 years³.

According to Musharbash F, Schill M et al. The Cox-maze IV procedure (CM4) performed concomitantly with other cardiac procedures has been shown to be effective for restoring sinus rhythm.

Conclusion

According to Our case, In ASD patient with AF, transcatheter ASD closure alone demonstrated AF recurrence after ASD closure alone. Cox Maze 4 operation for the treatment of unresponsive or medically recurrent Afib during concomitant cardiac surgeries in ACHD is a safe and an effective procedure.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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